

MOTIVATIONAL DRIVERS IN ADVENTURE TOURISM AND THEIR IMPACT ON DESTINATION LOYALTY

Rao Priyanka Anjali

Department of Tourism, Indian Academy Degree College, Bangalore, India

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Abstract: Adventure tourism continuous to expand and become one of the largest and fast-growing sectors that contributed to the economy of nation. The growth of tourism sector in the global economy brought quick and dramatic change in the coming years as result of the technological development and advancement in air and sea. Tourist motivation was one of the utmost crucial factors that influenced one to make decision to travel away from home. Motivation is a part of need that can encourage people to participate in tourist activities. Motivation is the external factor that drew people to a particular travel destination. Over a selection of alternative destination. Motivation would be seen a driving internal and external force that influenced people to travel away from home which it was acknowledged. An important framework to examine the motivation on tourist visitation behavior was the push and pull factor. Tourist might have more than one motive in choosing a particular destination. The study also states that different push and pull motivational factor influenced people not only in making decision to travel but also in choosing the specific travel destination. Push factor that motivates people to leave their homes and pull factor which drew individual to travel to a specific tourism destination. Customer satisfaction is a short-term emotional reaction to a specific service performance. Destination loyalty is the most important concept that plays a vital role in retaining tourist. Recommendation is described as the act of disseminating positive word of mouth to other. The paper will help us to understand how push and pull factor influence the tourists for decision making and push factor plays a vital role for in tourism.

Keywords: Destination loyalty; Decision making; Tourist motivation; Tourist visitation

INTRODUCTION

Tourist motivation is the external motives in tourism that can influence tourist and pull them towards subsequent decision, tourist gets motivated by external factors such as pull factors. Travel motivation is the individual desire and need for pleasure that is connected to travel, thrill, entertainment and excitement. Most push factors are intrinsic motivators such as escape, prestige, personality development and social interaction. Pull factors emerge due to attractiveness of a destination, recreation and cultural attractions. Tourist motivation is an important factor in understanding tourist behavior in relation to destination choice, Li and Zhang and reported that individuals travel patterns are closely related to psychological patterns which can be used to examine the factors that motivate people to travel [1]. Hill motives as a response to psychosomatics exhaustion.

Traveler's behavior-needs and wants through Maslow's hierarchy of needs. The UNWTOs annual report states that the importance of youth travel stating that it has become one of the fastest growing segments and the number of youth travelers is increasing. Buffa's study of young tourists' profiles and attitudes revealed that the choice of destination motivation discovered new cultures, new landscapes, natural and artistic heritage and contact with local community.

Backpackers prefer to discover new places in independent and alternative ways and strengthen ties or create new ties with backpacker communities. According to Richards, the flash packer is the most connected traveler, using social media frequently and being more likely to mix and blur work and leisure.'

Regarding the use of new information and communication technologies, young adventure tourists represent the highest percentage of utilizing the technologies. Young tourists 'Participate actively in various activities [2].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Push and pull motivational factor

Push factors is called as intrinsic factors or internal drives that urge individuals to travel. These are associated with factors such as for rest, recreation, adventure and escape and a desire to 'get away from it all'. Push factors encourage people to travel, representing individuals' socio-psychological needs. Pull factors are mostly associated with destinations' amenities, for example, service quality, prices and infrastructure. Pull factors come from within destinations, but these factors can help trigger push factors. Destinations thus should be able to meet customers' expectations in terms of prices, facilities (e.g. accommodation, transportation, food, restaurants and amusement parks) and most importantly, the level of quality provided. This means that, from time to time, destination managers need to augment their offers in ways that satisfy customers' needs and desires [3].

- Travel motivation is perceived as one of the most useful methods to understand tourists demand and their behaviour and to predict their decision-making procedure.
- Motivation can be escape, relaxation, self-exploration, prestige, enhancement of kinship, social interaction and regression while cultural motives involved only novelty, education.
- Behavioural intentions have been defined as the "degree to which a person has formulated conscious plans to perform or not some specified future behaviours".
- HOLSAT model also measures satisfaction based on comparison between tourist's expectation and experience towards attributes of destination.
- Tourist's satisfaction is also seen as a post purchase construct. Tourists' satisfaction is the result between tourist experience and tourist's expectation about an activity.

A social psychological model of tourist's motivation was proposed

- Escape from the personal environment such as one own problem or trouble.
- Getting away from the interpersonal environment such as colleagues, friends or family.
- Looking for personal intrinsic seeking interpersonal rewards for instance, meeting new people in the destination or in a travel group.
- Internal performance-thrill, fear, control, skill, achievement, fitness and risk.
- Nature, art and spirituality.
- Friends, image, escape and social position [4]. **Tourists' destination loyalty**

Motivations can be-escape, relaxation, self-exploration, prestige, enhancement of kinship, social interaction and regression while cultural motives involved only novelty, education. Motivations such as the desire to relax, rest, stay inactive are now replaced with the desire to discover new places, to learn, meet people, to live new experiences.

Increasingly more tourists want holidays that stimulate them mentally. Extrinsic motivation is a person motivation for a given behavior can be affected by a positive motivation or by unwillingness. According to Alegre and Cladera, the decision to revisit a destination is complex which involves numerous factors as prior experience, tourist motivations and satisfaction of stay. Adventure behavior may be defined as the behavior of an individual who is taking part in an adventure activity that involves risk an uncertain outcome and potential danger. Travel motivation is perceived as one of the most useful methods to understand tourists demand and their behavior and to predict their decision-making procedure [5].

Tourists are attracted because of the destination attraction, activities, amenities, climate, culture and food and accessibility. The study also shows that push factor is plays a major role in motivation individual to travel than pull factors. The pull factors are external motivational factors such as better health, higher income, more free time and the attractiveness of the physical environment, advertising campaign, promotion packages and word of mouth. Tourist's behavior towards adventure activities is explained by two elements that is the satisfaction level and loyalty towards tourism products. If a tourist is satisfied it is not necessary, that he may opt for the same activity or may purchase it often but on the other hand if a tourist is loyal there are more chances that he will participate in the activity frequently and refer others to experience the same. It is believed that destinations with more positive images attract more tourists and destination image also affects the behavioral intentions of customers. Attitude of a tourist is categorized into positive and negative and differs from person to person. Tourist's carries different perception before experiencing the thrill or risk from an activity, this perception can be seen on how they react towards a particular activity (Figure 1) [6].

Figure 1: Six competitive advantages through customer satisfaction.

Satisfaction is used for long term success for the destination and it brings benefits to the stakeholder. Customer satisfaction includes word of mouth, consumers complaining behavior, brand loyalty, continence, recommendation, repurchase intention. Visitor's satisfaction also leads to the high level of satisfaction that leads to encourage tourist revisit the destination, satisfied tourists also tell their relatives and friends, giving them free advertisement and help them to take part in travel to the destination or participate in the activities. A satisfied tourist is willing to pay higher price. Repeated purchase and positive word of mouth reduces business cost [7]. Satisfaction is defined as the consumers' overall cognitive or affective response to product use and consumers' judgment of whether a product provides a pleasurable level of consumption related fulfilment. A trip of tourists visiting a destination and experiencing and this can happen through natural and cultural destination attributes which affects tourist's perceptions of service quality and pricing.

Objective of the study

- To examine motivational factors among tourist in adventure activities.
- To find out the relationship between tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty for adventure activities in Karnataka [8].

Need of the study

The study will help us to understand tourist behavioural patterns and motivational factors as one of the most useful methods to know tourist demands and their behaviors and what motivates them to travel by predicting their decision making, while they choose adventure activities.

Gap of the study

There is not much study focused on tourist's behavioral intensions and destination loyalty by adventure tourists who are participating in adventure activities for the first time [9].

Limitation of the study

The study should assess the role of gender for the need of achievement in adventure activity. It is difficult to assess the tourist's experience who are participating in adventure activities for the first time. Limitation of the study shows that there is a lot of challenge in providing reliable, valid and useful ways to monitor tourist's behavior. Though the process of monitoring tourist behavior is time-consuming and financially demanding.

Hypothesis

- There is a relationship between tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty.
- Destination attribute will influence the selection of adventure activities [10].

Sample technique

Sample size: 400.

Sampling method: Random sampling and stratified sampling. After the pilot study out of 38 question and 26 question were finalized. Sample size will be calculated using sample size calculation formulae developed by Cochran. Sample size formula:

$$\frac{(Z\text{-Score})^2 * SD * (1-SD)}{(\text{Margin of Error})^2}$$

Data collection

This study is descriptive research with quantitative approach. Descriptive research is research which is intended to describe characteristic of variable. In this study quantitative data will primary data source for analysis while qualitative information would be used as secondary data source to support data analysis and also would be used to determine attributes which will be analyzed.

- Data was collected through primary and secondary sources.
- Primary source: Tourist in Karnataka
- Tool for data collection: Questionnaire survey using Google forms.
- Secondary sources: Research articles and reports.
- Data was also collected by distributing hard copies of questionnaires to the tourist who have participated and experienced adventure activity [11].

DISCUSSION

The major finding of the study is that tourists are influenced and motivated to travel more because of pull factor than push factor. Achievement and risk taking, ego enhancement, novelty and knowledge seeking and exciting experience were found to be the most significance motivation related to the reason for travel and choosing to participate in adventure tourism. Motivation can be psychological or physical prestigious or social fantasy and cultural. Travel motivation is perceived as one of the most useful methods to understand tourists demand and their behavior and to predict their decision-making procedure [12].

Tourist overall satisfaction is determined by destination image and attribute satisfaction. Tourist attribute satisfaction is also directly influenced by destination image and destination loyalty is in turn influenced by overall satisfaction. It is believed that destinations with more positive images will more likely be included in the process of decision making. Destination image also affects the behavioral intentions of customers. Customer loyalty towards a product or brand is generally conceptualized as behavior. Behavior loyalty refers to repeated purchase while attitudinal loyalty refers to the preference and favorable attitude of tourists towards particular brand.

According to the tourists participated in winter and summer are the most preferred season for the tourists for adventure activities. Tourists feel relaxed if they travel with their friends and few tourists' participants do not enjoy adventure travel if they travel alone. Most of the tourists used information resources of travelers are from travel agencies and mouth to mouth recommendation and internet. According to the tourist they are less informed by print media, sources related by region and broadcast media. They consider that the most useful channel is personal recommendation [13].

CONCLUSION

Loyal tourists tend to spend less money than first times their spending will at least provide positive economic impacts to the destination and their word of mouth will encourage others first time to visit to destination. Destination marketing marketers must understand what motivates and attracts tourists to visit certain destination and how to satisfy these needs to develop effective destination marketing strategies. Motivation has played a central role in understanding travel behavior and decision making. The push and pull framework is a frequently used methods to explain tourists behavior.

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